

Sustainable Careers for Researcher Empowerment

WP7 *Exploitation Plan*

Deliverable 7.2: Exploitation Plan

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1. Introduction

SECURE Work Package 7 (WP7) Exploitation Plan (D7.2) – is an internal project document describing the actions and tools for the exploitation of the project results. It offers a comprehensive exploitation support strategy, including objectives of exploitation and technical choices towards the most promising directions for wider impact. The goal is to maximize the opportunities for innovation and further development and usage of the project results.

Exploitation Plan establishes the basis for the development of a common exploitation action during the project in order to secure medium- and long-term project impact goals. This is a document for the use of all the partners involved in SECURE project. The Deliverable D7.2 is designated as public regarding the dissemination level. The deliverable is live and will be modified according to the project needs during project's duration. This deliverable will be periodically updated, with new the strategies of the project as well as identify in detail the stakeholders, actions, tools, materials, KPIs and procedures agreed.

The impacts of the exploitation support activities will be monitored and evaluated by the work package leader, CPN, and project partners periodically and the Deliverable modified accordingly. The results of the strategies implemented will be made visible at the end of project activities in the Final Dissemination, Communications & Exploitation Report (D7.3, M24).

2. About the SECURE project

The Sustainable Careers for Researcher Empowerment (SECURE) project will develop coordination and support measures to create, trial, implement, and mainstream a common Research Career Framework (RCF) that offers a set of options to support organisations in the recruitment, employment, training, development, progression, and mobility of researchers with the aim of improving research careers and reducing career precarity.

During its two-year duration, the project consortium will develop, produce and launch:

- **State-of-the-art on Research Careers (WP1)** – Develop a comprehensive Research Career Framework integrating relevant existing policies. More details about this work package can be found in project grant agreement.
- **SECURE Research Career Framework (WP2)** – Engage research stakeholders for co-design and validation of the Research Career Framework. More details about this work package can be found in project grant agreement.
- **Tenure Track-Like Models (WP3)** – Develop a range of tenure track-like models integrating best practices from existing use cases. More details about this work package can be found in project grant agreement.
- **Trialing the Research Career Framework (WP4)** – Conduct trials at organisations to implement, test, and refine the Research Career Framework. More details about this work package can be found in project grant agreement.
- **Mainstreaming the Research Career Framework (WP5)** – Mainstream the Research Career Framework through EURAXESS, policy briefs, and a summit and policy roundtable. More details about this work package can be found in project grant agreement.

3. WP 7 – Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation

Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation is an important part of the Horizon Europe projects that all partner must take part in. Communicating European projects should aim at how research and innovation are contributing to an “Innovation Union”. This objective is divided into two complementary activities:

Dissemination and communication activities oriented to show the attractiveness of the results achieved and their impact towards a target audience composed of key stakeholders identified, consumers, journalists and general public. Dissemination and communication activities will be described in this document (D7.1).

Exploitation actions will establish the main pillars for a future uptake plan of the most promising and mature results generated in the project. The exploitation strategy will identify technical choices towards the most promising directions, thus maximizing the opportunities for innovation and further development and usage of the project results. Exploitation actions will be described in the separate deliverable, the Exploitation Plan (D7.2).

Main objective of the work package 7 is to support the previous packages and through appropriate strategic measures diffuse and propagate the project goals, progress, results to reach target audiences and wider public, thus provide visibility of project aims and actions. The aim is to communicate with and reach out to relevant stakeholder groups and wider public, and to inform about the use and benefits of the project for them. Subsequently, the goal is to stimulate further initiatives that can lead to the wider impact beyond the scope of the project, by supporting appropriate exploitation of project results in medium- and long-term timeframe. The general goal is for project to bring forth scientific, techno-economic and societal impact in the field of research careers, overcoming precarity and inciting new approaches in order to support and evolve more sustainable careers.

Center for the Promotion of Science (CPN) is the leader of the work package seven and its activities, along with the support of all project partners and their channels in dissemination of project results. Dissemination, Communication, and Exploitation Committee is established for planning and coordinating these activities and will be meeting monthly, every second week of the month, on Thursday at 11am CEST. The Committee consists of the members of partner organisations of this project, namely from CPN, ICoRSA, PLOCAN, TGB, Vitae and EurSc. The Committee is responsible for developing a focused strategy on how to promote the project and its results. The activities are carried out throughout the duration of the project.

Work package 7 related materials and resources can be accessed [here](#) .

3.1 Objectives of the Exploitation

The main objective of the exploitation plan is to utilize project results for further societal and scientific use by concretizing the value and impact of the project framework. In this sense, main exploitable outputs of this project are:

- State-of-the-art on Research Careers (WP1)
- SECURE Research Career Framework (WP2)
- Tenure Track-Like Models (WP3)
- Implementation Report by Trial Organisations (WP4)
- Mainstreaming Plan and Policy Briefs (WP5)

Primary project legacy lies in the Research Career Framework and Tenure Track-like Models, which will be rolled out in trial organisations, namely by partners PLOCAN, UCY, UNIRI, UNL and UEFISCDI. Policy briefs and Mainstreaming Plan provide details on the continued evolution of the implemented SECURE framework and models within the respective organisational procedures. Along with mentioned outputs, the State-of-the-art on Research Careers is another resource for future research.

3.2 Target Groups of the Exploitation

The primary target groups are research institutions and academia, as well as policy makers and governmental institutions that could be interested in implementing the main project outputs, both on national levels and on the wider EU level or through the regional initiatives.

Wider secondary target groups are the societal actors such as citizens, public organisations, industry and civil society organisations, especially ones relating to SECURE topics, as valuable mediators that can help the further implementation of project results in their own and other already existing communities and initiatives.

Additionally, to maximise its impact, project will liaise with EURAXESS and other WIDERA-ERA projects, especially Action 4, creating synergies with the awarded OPUS project under HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-ERA-01-45, where several SECURE partners are also collaborating, with sister project such as DocTalent4EU. The strong existing network of the consortium will be exploited to advertise best practices in career frameworks (CF), responsible research and innovation (RRI) and open science (OS).

The long-term sustainability of exploitable will be primarily ensured by the coordinator PLOCAN, who pledges to support and maintain the websites of its RRI and SSH projects, including SECURE for up to a period of 10 years post project. This ensures the free accessibility of all the project exploitables for further use.

3.3 Desired Impact

The goal of the exploitation actions is to bring forth the scientific, techno-economic and societal impact of project results beyond the duration of the project. Exploitation goals tie closely with the desired impact goals of the project. Project outputs are intended to be major undertakings with an impact spreading beyond the duration on the project, namely:

- Medium impact (up to 5 years after the project end)
- Long-term impact (up to 20 years after the project ends)

The projected impact for SECURE project is as follows:

- Impact through creating the RCF as a common researchers' career structure, recognising the diversification of careers, interinstitutional, international and intersectoral mobility, and competences gained and needed by PhD candidates and postdocs within and outside academia, building on existing best practices and linked to ESCO, Charter & Code, the new European Researcher Competency Framework and recent Council Recommendations.
- Impact through developing new Tenure Track-Like models improving career development and reducing precarity in academia, including requirements for professional development and career progression at particular career transition points as well as recommendations on intersectoral mobility and involving the non-

academic sector from the onset in training and career development of PhD candidates.

- Impact through mainstreaming the RCF and TTL models through practical examples of successful trials, responding to stakeholder feedback, extensive consultation and dissemination activities and embedding within the EURAXESS network including the service centres, newly-established EURAXESS talent management hubs, and the ERA Talent Platform that is currently being developed.

Impact and its outcomes tie closely to the exploitation, such as that through the exploitation tools and actions we get to the desired midterm and longterm impact. All target estimates for outcomes below are based on the consulted expertise of the project consortium. The following outcomes are envisioned:

3.3.1 SECURE Outcome 1

Common academic researchers’ career framework, including new diversification of careers in academia and linking it to the updated ESCO qualifications:

The implementation of the Research Career Framework will reduce precarity of employment by identifying realistic career progression requirements, required funding, career mentoring and professional development provision. Each career progression stage will be linked to ESCO competencies to ensure standard recognition. Research performing organisations, Research Financing Organisations and industry trials will assess and ensure the practical implementation of the Research Career Framework to ensure short- and medium-term impact.

The long-term impacts will be more consistency and harmonisation of researcher careers titles & levels across the EU facilitating researcher mobility and reducing precarity; increased transparency of academic career structures, increasing the attractiveness of research careers and enhancing bi-directional intersectoral mobility; improved sustainability of research careers leading to greater scientific quality and research excellence, stronger knowledge transfer, innovation and exploitation of R&D.

Scientific Impact:

	Description	Why
Medium-term (5+ years)	Increased number of collaboration papers	Increased job security, more structured career progression and attractiveness of research careers through the implementation of the RCF frees up capacities for higher quality science, improved dissemination and translation into innovation (c.f. ERC success story).
	Increased OA publications	
	Increased number of open/FAIR data sets	
	Increased open research / societal engagement	
Long-term (10+ years)	Increased translation of research into innovation	If SECURE CF adopted EU wide, EU publications and patents increase, and FAIR implemented EU-wide
	Increased number of patents / spinouts	
	Increased inter-connectiveness of the R&I ecosystem	

Reference: [Domestic researchers with longer careers generate higher average citation impact](#) (ResearchGate)

Techno-Economic Impact: *target estimated by consortium expertise ** to be Validated by ICoRSA annual survey

	Description	Target
Medium-term (5+ years)	YERUN increases their RPO membership numbers as front runner in sustainable researcher careers	20%*
Long-term	Research careers improve and increase economic benefits for researchers	

(10+ years)	Increased career stability attracts and retains high quality researchers, increasing R&I revenue***	20% Senior researchers
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***Reference: Research and Innovation Outreach Unit G1 – ‘ERA and country intelligence’ [Link](#)

Societal Impact: *target estimated by consortium expertise ** to be Validated by ICoRSA annual survey

	Description	Targets
Medium-term (5+ years)	Researchers are aware of the RCF. Researchers recognise the competences they need to progress to the next stage of their career. Researchers understand the transferable nature of their competences into other employment sectors.	Survey of ICORSA, MCAA, EuDOC researchers: 50% of are aware of the RCF 25% recognise the competences to progress their career 25% understand the transferability of their competences.
	Employers beyond academia recognise researcher competencies.	Survey of ADOC, ABIS employers: 20% recognise researchers' competencies
Long-term (10+ years)	Researchers have better CVs, careers prospects and mobility	Increase in mobility by 20%**
	Increase in EU RPOs and RFOs with TTL systems for early career researchers	33% of RPOs; 33% of RFOs
	EU universities using SECURE RCF	50% of universities (potentially measured through EUA survey)
	Increased researcher mobility across the EU due to standardised competency recognition across EU.	Increase in mobility by 20%
	Increased interconnected knowledge ecosystem, knowledge creation, circulation and use	

Figures 1-2: Projected impact for Outcome 1. Source: SECURE Grant Agreement.

3.3.2 SECURE Outcome 2

Developing Tenure Track-Like systems to improve career development and decrease precarity in academia:

Tenure track systems currently provide recognised career progression structures and are effective in attracting high-potential and highly-skilled researchers with the possibility of achieving a permanent academic career. The SECURE TTL model will extend the range of TTL options to cater for a wider range of researchers and member states' / and RPOs' needs. Medium-term impacts will be achieved by increased attractive long-term career options (that may or may not result in permanent positions) and increased retention of researchers. Long-term impact is a more secure research workforce, with fewer talented researchers lost due to poor career progression options and feeling more able to invest time in research and associated translation activities, leading to increased research & innovation for the ERA.

Scientific Impact Description: *target estimates made after consultation with consortium expertise, ** to be verified Eurstat

	Description	Targets
Medium-term (5+ years)	Rankings of YERUN universities implementing TTL increase due to increased attractiveness as employers	20% increase*
Long-term (10+ years)	Researchers will produce better quality research, improving their career prospects. Better quality scientific research has benefits for society.	10% increase in scientific publications**

Reference: [Domestic researchers with longer careers generate higher average citation impact](#)

Techno-Economic Impact: *target estimates made after consultation with consortium expertise, ** to be verified Eurstat

	Description	Targets
Medium-term (5+ years)	Senior researchers on TT will achieve increased research grant funding	20%*
Long-term (10+ years)	Improved R&I output in EU due to more stable and experienced senior workforce	5% increase in R&I index**

Societal Impact: * to be verified via ICoRSA annual survey on career progression

	Description	Targets
Medium-term (5+ years)	Researchers in the pilot RPOs will have higher chance of structured career progression due to the implementation of TTL systems.	20% increased likelihood of researcher career progress*
Long-term (10+ years)	TTL systems enable more EU researchers to stay longer in research careers with less stress, higher productivity and stronger linkages and easier transitions between academia and other employment sectors.	20% increase in intersectoral mobility of researchers

Figures 3-4: Projected impact for Outcome 2. Source: SECURE Grant Agreement.

3.3.3 SECURE Outcome 3

Mainstreaming training practices, career development, value creation and career framework knowledge hubs:

Usually, European career frameworks stay at EU level without national or regional adoption. The SECURE RCF and TTL models will link the Charter & Code, revised ESCO, new European Research Competency Framework, and recent Council Recommendations. The trials in WP3 & WP4 will demonstrate effective approaches and showcase the added value by the consolidated RCF and TTL models. The impact is further leveraged beyond the immediate network via the recently launched EURAXESS talent management hubs and the wider EURAXESS networks. The consolidated RCF and a range of concrete options for TTL models provide a blueprint to manage and counteract an increasing volatile, uncertain, complex and ambiguous (VUCA) environment in research and education. Partners with access to national and regional hubs will locally engage research staff associations, RPOs and RFOs to advocate the RCF. BZN will also serve as a point of contact for dissemination and impact towards the European EURAXESS network of more than 600 service centres for a two-way communication and expertise exchange towards the development of the ERA Talent Platform.

Scientific Impact Description: * Partner best estimate

	Description	Targets
Medium-term (5+ years)	Rankings of YERUN universities increases by implementing RCF with embedded training and increased intersectoral mobility	Estimated 20% increase in ranking*
	Increased number of Open Access publications from YERUN universities.	Estimated 20% increase in OA
Long-term (10+ years)	Increased number of RPOs adopting the SECURE RCF will result in a EU research workforce with more developed transferable competences and more intersectorally mobile increasing research and innovation output across the ERA	Estimated 20% in EU wide R&I index (to be verified by EIS RIS**)

** <https://ec.europa.eu/research-and-innovation/en/statistics/performance-indicators/european-innovation-scoreboard/eis>

Techno-Economic Impact: * RPO Partners' best estimate, to be verified by RPO approx. 5 years after project ends.

	Description	Targets
Medium-term (5+ years)	Pilot RPOs will see increases in successful funding applications due to a more highly-skilled and trained research workforce	20% increase *
	YERUN and researcher associations will expand their membership due to their pioneering role the SECURE RCF project	20% increase in membership*
Long-term (10+ years)	Intersectoral mobility leads to increase in R&I and patent outputs by YERUN universities implementing SECURE RCF and TTL models	20-40% increase in patents**

** reference: <https://publications.jrc.ec.europa.eu/repository/handle/JRC102534>

Societal Impact: (target estimates made after consultation with consortium expertise)

	Description	Targets
Medium-term (5+ years)	Increased number of public outreach and citizen science activities at YERUN pilot universities	Estimated 20%

Long-term (10+ years)	EU wide researcher workforce with more ease of access to intersectoral mobility and more highly trained will be a more productive and content workforce leading to higher productivity and R&I output for the ERA	Estimated 20% in EU-wide R&I index (to be verified by EIS RIS**)
	Reduced precarity of PhD candidates and postdocs, as indicated by a reduction in fixed-term contracts (less than 3 years).	Reduction by 20% at YERUN universities

Figures 5-6: Projected impact for Outcome 2. Source: SECURE Grant Agreement.

3.4 Project Exploitables and Exploitation Tools & Actions

In order to achieve the exploitation goals and drive to the desired outcomes above, work package seven will take actions towards exploitation and building relationships with key stakeholders and networks that could be using project outputs to make a significant change in practice.

Table 1: Main project exploitables and exploitation tools/actions

Exploitable	Exploitation Tools/Actions
State-of-the-art on Research Careers	The comprehensive literature review on research careers will be openly accessible via website for further use.
SECURE Research Career Framework	Besides the RCF document format itself and the RCF infographics, the research career framework will be openly accessible via an interactive tool on the project website, with options for stakeholders to export the chosen data for further use.
Tenure Track-Like Models	Besides being integrated in the RCF itself, the structure of the TTL models will be visually presented and explained via infographics on the project website, openly accessible and used as an example for the future uptake and implementation of these models. Additionally, will be presented through factsheets and brochures to the wider public, citizens and industry.
Implementation Report by Trial Organisations	The report on the piloting actions by six partners (4 RPOs, 1 RFO and 1 recruitment agency) will include the recommendations for implementation of the TTL models. From these conclusions a training guide will be produced, as a digital visually appealing booklet guide for the institutions interested in further exploring or implementing the TTL models, available on the project website. Additionally, CPN will conduct interviews with piloting partners after the completion of the pilots to gather more experiential firsthand information on the implementation process itself, which may help shape the further uptakes.
Mainstreaming Plan and Policy Brief	Mainstreaming the RCF will be managed by the EURAXESS network via EURAXESS service centres, talent management hubs, and ERA Talent Platform. The Policy Brief will be used to build awareness and promote the uptake of the RCF, specifically focusing on key aspects for the stakeholder community. Lead in this action is the EuroSc partner and CPN will be in charge with exploiting the Policy Brief itself.

Additionally all the exploitables will be addressed and presented at the final summit of the project and the policy roundtable to the key stakeholders from various backgrounds. This will ensure further uptake and exploitation of the main project results and outputs.

Moreover, work package seven will be in consultation, participation and agreement with the project consortium, mapping out important stakeholders and the most promising directions for maximizing the opportunities for innovation and further development and usage of the project results. In the two years duration of the project, work package seven will conduct a series of (online or in person) meetings with chosen stakeholders that are mapped out as holding the most potential for further exploitation actions. Meetings will include representatives of policy makers and governmental representatives, research associations and organisations, both on national and EU level, and other suitable contacts that could be involved in uptake of project results and their implementation. Exploitation actions during project duration will work towards making concrete partner agreements or plans for the use of project results after the project end.

Table 2: Exploitation support actions by WP7 lead during the project duration

Support action steps	Target stakeholders	Desired outcomes
1. Mapping out the important exploitation stakeholders outside of the project consortium	Policy makers and governmental representatives; higher education representatives; industry representatives; both on national, regional and EU level	Concrete agreements or plans on using the project outputs beyond the scope of the project, if possible.
2. Series of online or in person meetings with chosen stakeholders to drive external collaboration		
3. Comprehensive meetings report with conclusions and possible next steps for exploitation mapped out		

Project partners themselves will use their best efforts to exploit the results directly or to have them exploited indirectly by another entity, in particular through transfer or licensing, up to four years after the end of the action. Additionally, within one year after the end of project, all project outputs and results will be published on the Horizon Results platform in order to boost the exploitation potential and possibly bring forth future collaborations.

Table 3: Exploitation support actions by project partners during the scope of project

Exploitables	Expected results	Target groups	Desired outcomes
Research Career Framework, Pilot Implementation Report, Policy Brief	Six trial organisations will complete a one-year initial implementation phase, which could lead to the implementation of the Research Career Framework after the project duration	RPO or RFO, Researchers, Industry, Policy	YERUN will advise remaining university members to adopt SECURE RCF, and UEF will recommend to other funding bodies
Research Career Framework, Policy Brief	Each step of the progression within the RCF is linked to ESCO competencies, enabling widespread recognition of the ESCO qualifications profiles	RPO or RFO, Researchers, Industry, Policy	The link between the RCF and ESCO will be mutually benefiting and enforcing
Research Career Framework, Pilot Implementation Report, Policy brief	WP3 will develop new Tenure Track-Like models for improved funding mechanisms, trialed in WP4, and recommendations to promote tenure tracks	RPO or RFO, Policy	UEF will embed new funding strategies for TT as part of the RCF
Research Career Framework, Policy Brief, State-of-the-Art on Research Careers	The RCF’s core mission is for improved career progress and less precarity	RPO and RFO, Researchers, Industry, Policy	EuDoc, ICoRSA, MCAA, Vitae, YERUN will disseminate the exploitables to these target groups to adopt
Research Career Framework, Policy brief, State-of-the-Art on Research Careers	State-of-the-Art and Policy brief will address inclusive gender equality needs to be accounted for in RCF	RPO or RFO, Researchers, Industry, Policy	Improved and inclusive gender equality in research career progression
Research Career Framework, Policy brief,	State-of-the-Art and Policy brief will address industry needs to be accounted for	Researchers, Industry, Policy	ABIS, ADOC, TGB and Vitae will disseminate RCF to these target groups,

State-of-the-Art on Research Careers	in Research Career Framework		industry will incorporate RCF in their research
Infographics about RCF	Societal and economic actors will have openly available information about SECURE for the easier uptake	Researchers, Societal actors, Economic actors	RCF infographic will increase public awareness and uptake about sustainable research careers
Infographics about RCF	Established two-way channel of communication and expertise exchange and for the easier uptake	Researchers	EURAXESS and existing partner hub/networks will advocate RCF

More detailed overview of the wider long-term impact and linkage to other projects and initiatives can be found in the project grant agreement. All the project exploitables can be utilized in the long term and tied with other similar existing initiatives for even wider impact and implementation, as described below.

Destination Wider Impact	SECURE wider Impact	Links & Comments
Reform and Enhance the EU R&I system	The RCF as an underpinning framework is intimately linked to the reform and enhancement of EU R&I system.	Knowledge Ecosystems
Higher scientific quality and stronger translation of R&I results into economy	The RCF will facilitate more structured and stable researcher careers providing increased opportunity for R&I impacts & resultant economic prosperity.	Knowledge ecosystems Error! Bookmark not defined.
Deepen the new ERA - “strive for better, employability to fully unlock the cooperation & connectivity in the ERA at researchers, programme, institutions”	The RCF will enhance the employability of researchers by highlighting their competencies and identify appropriate working conditions and career progression steps.	ECOMP 3.B
Synergies between research & innovation and higher education policies and programmes	The RCF will reflect how R&I activities sit within the higher education environment and the competences that researchers need to be successful, including teaching abilities.	EU R&I policy
Increased number of interconnected knowledge ecosystems, circulation and use	The importance, value and the skills needed for interinstitutional and intersectoral mobility will be embedded in the RCF to increase interconnectivity.	New ERA Hubs
Researchers benefit from attractive careers	The RCF provides a framework to make research careers more attractive and thereby “ensure the availability of highly skilled human resources”.	EuroParl COM(2020) 628
Inclusive gender equality is promoted in the European research and innovation system	The RCF will reflect the diversity of researchers, including gender, embedding the importance of an open, inclusive and supportive research environment as a key priority.	SWD 2020
A more open and inclusive research and innovation system		CDN I Furaxess
Increased alignment of strategic research with society needs, expectations and values	The societal need of a secure and sustainable research career will be enshrined and reinforced by the RCF.	IANUS
Knowledge and a highly skilled workforce circulate freely	The RCF will enshrine the transferability of researcher competences and promote two-way porosity at key transition points throughout the RCF.	OECD

Figure 6: Wider long-term projected impact and linkage to other existing initiatives. Source: SECURE Grant Agreement.

4. Guiding Principles in Exploitation

Regarding exploitation, project outputs will follow the FAIR and open science principles. Project will employ the FAIR principles to make relevant publications and data produced in the project findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable. The publications will involve all public deliverable reports and peer-reviewed scientific publications stemming from the project. The project consortium will ensure that a data steward from a partner organisation supports the DMP and FAIRification of all publications and data. The project consortium aims to be as open as possible with project publications and data which will be deposited and made available in a trusted repository, such as Github and Zenodo. Open access to project publications and data will be ensured via the repository as soon as possible and within deadlines set in the DMP.

All project deliverables, guidelines, toolkits and reports will be openly published. The project consortium will ensure Open Access to relevant publications and data resulting from the project. All project partners agree to provide full and immediate Open Access under a CC BY licence to the published version of their publications and data, whereby the project strives to be as open as possible and as closed as necessary, unless an embargo or restriction is necessary and in line with EC regulations. All relevant metadata will be openly published under a CC0 licence. The project has allocated associated costs in the budget to cover a number of publication fees in relevant full Open Access venues. Project partners agree to retain sufficient intellectual property rights on their publications and data as authors to comply with Open Access requirements.

As a CSA project, no patent or IP issues should arise. However, the Consortium Agreement will clearly specify the IP background, which will be made available for use within the consortium. Any IP foreground produced during the project will be protected and managed by the SECURE SC with a joint ownership among the consortium partners. A comprehensive review of existing state-of-the-art and a patent prior to the proposal identified no potential conflicts with existing knowledge of a third party.

Sustainable Careers for Researcher Empowerment

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SECURE PROJECT

IF YOU WOULD LIKE TO KNOW MORE ABOUT
OUR PROJECT ACTIVITIES

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